

Computer Vision Analysis of War-Related Visual Culture: Patterns and Symbols in Russia- Ukraine Conflict Art

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This project began in 2022 as an investigation into emerging visual responses to the war in Ukraine. Using Google Custom Search API and Python library `google_images_search`, I systematically collected approximately 5,000 visual artifacts through about 30 Google search queries in Russian, Ukrainian, English, German, and French. The collection focuses on artistic responses – excluding photography – to examine how both professional artists and ordinary people worldwide interpret and represent the conflict through creative expression. After formal duplicate removal, the repository spans diverse artistic forms from street art and graffiti to digital memes, children's drawings, and fine art, creating a deduplicated physical repository for iconographic study.

The analytical framework centers on a Vision Transformer model (Dosovitskiy et al. 2021) pre-trained on 14 million images categorized into more than 20,000 classes. This model functions similarly to BERT but processes images instead of text, allowing grouping of artworks by recognizing complex visual patterns and themes. Multi-modal techniques are being developed to align visual data with associated textual metadata extracted from contexts where images are mentioned.

Initial clustering analysis revealed distinct typologies distinguishing children's drawings from street art, murals from digital memes, identifying thematic nodes around military iconography, national flags, and political figure representations. An object detection algorithm successfully identified recurring symbols including blue-yellow birds representing Ukrainian identity, cats, bears, and gendered archetypes showing civilian figures predominantly depicted as women and girls while men appear almost always in military or political leadership roles. Similar patterns have been documented in previous research on political iconography and visual propaganda (Basilio 2014; Clark 1997; Dauber & Winkler 2014; Müller 2007). Gender representation analysis reveals strong patterns across the dataset, this pattern becomes especially notable considering the linguistic context, where terms like *'motherland'* (родина) are feminine in Slavic languages, potentially influencing artistic representation across traditionally patriarchal societies like Russia and Ukraine. Even when child boys appear in artworks, they

are usually depicted as fighting figures, as seen in Banksy's street art where a boy fights with Putin.

Historical parallels emerged prominently, featuring Putin-Hitler hybrid imagery, collages combining Putin, Stalin and Hitler together, and fascist symbolism including swastikas overlaying Russian flags – visual strategies consistent with established patterns in propaganda research where dictatorial figures are deliberately associated with historical villains to delegitimize power (Jowett & O'Donnell 2019).

The analysis uncovered temporal evolution in iconographic themes. Ships became a significant motif in art at the beginning of the war, referring to the first day of invasion and the famous *"Russian warship, go f*** yourself"* Snake Island incident appearing in multiple artworks. This evolution correlates with specific conflict events, demonstrating how artistic responses adapt to unfolding wartime narratives – a phenomenon well-documented in visual culture studies of previous conflicts (Chouliaraki 2013).

Particularly significant spatial patterns emerged around contextualization practices. Anti-Russian art appears near embassy buildings in various countries, creating symbolic dialogue through urban space, with both sides of the conflict using opposing countries embassies for artistic statements. Moscow uses the American embassy building for light shows supporting the war, while Russian embassy areas in other countries are targeted for anti-war art. In Ukraine, professional street artists like Banksy often choose war-damaged or destroyed buildings as canvases, transforming sites of destruction into powerful artistic statements. Border zones serve as powerful sites for political expression, exemplified by the huge anti-Russia poster installed on the Estonian-Russian border. These location choices amplify artwork messages through strategic placement rather than random distribution, reflecting broader patterns in political street art geography (Riggle 2010).

Recent political developments, including Donald Trump's 2024 election, have initiated emergence of new war-motivated imagery featuring hybrid Trump-Putin representations, providing valuable comparative material for analyzing how geopolitical changes influence iconographic evolution in real-time. This dynamic corpus demonstrates the relevance of developed methods for analyzing rapidly evolving cultural phenomena.

This work demonstrates how computer vision techniques can decode complex cultural narratives embedded in visual artifacts, preserving ephemeral cultural artifacts as historical evidence while offering methodological templates for similar studies in other geopolitical contexts

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